

1 **NOTICE: This is a non-peer-reviewed preprint of the article published in Biological Journal of the Linnean**
2 **Society.**

3 **The final, peer-reviewed version of record is available online via its Digital Object Identifier (DOI):**
4 **<https://doi.org/10.1093/biolinnean/blaf084>**

5 **Link: [https://academic.oup.com/biolinnean/article-](https://academic.oup.com/biolinnean/article-abstract/doi/10.1093/biolinnean/blaf084/8271903?utm_source=advanceaccess&utm_campaign=biolinnean&utm_medium=email)**
6 **[abstract/doi/10.1093/biolinnean/blaf084/8271903?utm_source=advanceaccess&utm_campaign=biolin](https://academic.oup.com/biolinnean/article-abstract/doi/10.1093/biolinnean/blaf084/8271903?utm_source=advanceaccess&utm_campaign=biolinnean&utm_medium=email)**
7 **[nean&utm_medium=email](https://academic.oup.com/biolinnean/article-abstract/doi/10.1093/biolinnean/blaf084/8271903?utm_source=advanceaccess&utm_campaign=biolinnean&utm_medium=email)**

8

35 **Abstract**

36 Macrorefugia are geographic regions where conditions (e.g., climate) remain favorable for species'
37 persistence over time, enabling species to persist and diversify during adverse environmental periods.

38 Our goal was to address whether isolated forest biomes, like the Andean and the Atlantic forests, act as a
39 macrorefugia system promoting biological diversification (i.e., in complex morphological traits), and to
40 evaluate biogeographical hypotheses of their connection. We studied 24 bird lineages with disjunct
41 populations or sublineages in both the Andean and Atlantic forest realms, modeled their niches across
42 current and past periods, and evaluated connectivity between regions. Subsequently, we tested whether
43 bird morphological variation is predicted by geographic isolation between forest biomes, climatic factors
44 and landscape resistance. Our findings support that the Andean and the Atlantic forest acted as a
45 macrorefugia, driving biological diversification. Refugia isolation and climate were significant drivers of
46 morphological variation in the studied birds. The main biogeographical connections between these forests
47 occurred during glacial periods, primarily through the southern Cerrado and its transition with the Chaco.
48 Finally, we identified niche conservatism between disjunct populations and lineages, suggesting that it may
49 be a lagging factor for phenotypic divergence between macrorefugia.

50

51 **Keywords**

52 Andean forests; Atlantic Forest; Circuitscape; ecological niche model; morphological divergence;
53 Quaternary; refugia hypothesis

54

55 1. Introduction

56 The refugia hypothesis postulates that Quaternary climatic cycles led to alternating phases of habitat
57 fragmentation and expansion, promoting divergence and allopatric speciation during periods of
58 fragmentation (Haffer 1969; Vanzolini and Williams 1970; Simpson Vuilleumier 1971; Van der Hammen
59 1974). Evolution in refugia systems has likely played a key role in biological diversification, especially in
60 shaping the population genetic structure of neutral markers (Wüster *et al.* 2005; Sérsic *et al.* 2011;
61 Cabanne *et al.* 2016; Musher *et al.* 2020; Bukowski *et al.* 2024). However, their role in driving the
62 evolution of complex traits, such as phenotypic characteristics, remains underexplored (Winger and Bates
63 2015; Trujillo-Arias *et al.* 2020).

64 Refugia are classified into macrorefugia, which are large and climatically stable regions supporting
65 diverse populations, and microrefugia, which are smaller and isolated spots within inhospitable landscapes
66 where species persist due to unique local microclimates (Rull 2014). The Andean and the Atlantic forests
67 (Fig. 1) have been proposed as a macrorefugia system (Trujillo-Arias *et al.* 2020). Despite being isolated by
68 a mosaic of savanna and dry forest biomes (i.e., the Caatinga, the Cerrado and the Chaco), they share
69 species and closely related lineages (Erize *et al.* 2006; Ridgely and Tudor 2009; Patterson *et al.* 2012),
70 suggesting past biological interchange. Within the framework of a macrorefugia system, these forest
71 biomes are likely in a fragmentation phase, and biological interchange may have happened during
72 previous expansion phases. These connections may have occurred during wetter periods that favored
73 rainforest growth and forest corridors over drier in-between regions. If Quaternary climatic cycles drove
74 forest dynamism (i.e., strong forest area fluctuation), forest organism community ranges should vary
75 between climate phases (i.e., between glacial and interglacial periods), while remaining similar between
76 equivalent climate periods (e.g., among interglacial phases). Alternatively, if climate cycles impacted
77 forests in a species-specific manner, or if did not impact at all, forest organism community ranges should
78 be constant across periods. Ecological Niche Models (ENMs) enable testing these predictions by
79 reconstructing and comparing species distributions across periods (Ribeiro *et al.* 2016).

80 In this context, two main geographical hypotheses explain the biological connections between the
81 Andean and Atlantic forests (Fig. 1). The Chaco corridor hypothesis proposes that gallery forests along the
82 main Chaco region (i.e., Bermejo and Pilcomayo rivers) expanded during Quaternary interglacial periods,
83 connecting the southern portions of Andean and Atlantic forests (Nores, 1992). However, this hypothesis
84 is weakly supported by paleontological and phylogeographical studies (Zurita *et al.* 2014; Trujillo-Arias *et*
85 *al.* 2017; Delgado *et al.* 2021; Ferreiro *et al.* 2024), and is primarily supported by a few ENM studies

86 (Turchetto-Zolet *et al.* 2016; Vergara *et al.* 2017). Alternatively, the Cerrado corridor hypothesis suggests
87 that gallery forests within the Cerrado acted as corridors between forests (Silva 1996), with support from
88 palynological research (Ledru *et al.* 1991; Ledru 1993), biogeographical studies (Oliveira-Filho and Ratter
89 1995), forest biomes niche models (Carnaval and Moritz 2008; Sobral-Souza *et al.* 2015) and bird
90 phylogeography (Trujillo-Arias *et al.* 2017, 2018, 2020; Cabanne *et al.* 2019). These studies highlighted the
91 southern Cerrado edge and its transition with the Chaco (hereafter referred as the Cerrado - Chaco
92 transition, or CCT) as a key region connecting the Andean and Atlantic forests during the Pleistocene.
93 Finally, double contacts through both the Chaco and Cerrado, either simultaneously or alternating over
94 time, remains a plausible scenario (Willis 1992). ENMs of species and lineages shared between these
95 forests could clarify where and when dispersal corridors enabled forest fauna to traverse suboptimal
96 regions.

97 Under a scenario of forest dynamism and macrorefugia, populations in range contraction phases
98 are expected to diverge by chance (e.g., genetic drift) or a combination of chance and deterministic
99 processes, like divergent selection due to ecological differences (Avice 2000; Moritz *et al.* 2000). Recent
100 studies reveal that disjunct populations or lineages from the Andean and Atlantic forests show varying
101 levels of phenotypic divergence and, in some may even represent sister species (Trujillo-Arias *et al.* 2017;
102 Cavarzere *et al.* 2024). Such differentiation likely originated from divergence and speciation within
103 macrorefugia (e.g., Rocha *et al.* 2014; Trujillo-Arias *et al.* 2017; Cabanne *et al.* 2019). However, although
104 studies of evolution in macrorefugia systems have primarily focused on population genetic structure of
105 neutral markers, the evolution of complex traits—such as phenotypic characteristics—remains relatively
106 underexplored (Papadopoulou and Knowles 2016; Zamudio *et al.* 2016). According to Trujillo-Arias *et al.*
107 (2020), if isolation and connectivity dynamics between macrorefugia have significantly influence biological
108 diversification, species with disjunct populations should exhibit, among multiple traits, a concordant
109 pattern of spatial variation associated with the geographic isolation between forests (Fig. 1). Conversely, if
110 connections allowed high and consistent gene flow, enough to preclude differentiation, shared species
111 would display no morphological divergence between forests.

112 While genetic drift contributes to population divergence in allopatric systems, natural selection
113 linked to ecological differences also plays a key role (Zamudio *et al.* 2016). Complex phenotypic traits,
114 closely tied to environmental interactions, typically evolve through natural selection. In this context, the
115 role of ecological niche in phenotypic evolution seems to be fundamental, as niche differences between
116 populations could shape patterns of adaptive change. Therefore, in a putative macrorefugia system such

117 as the Andean and Atlantic forests, niche divergence is expected to act in conjunction with isolation as a
118 main driver of biological diversification. However, ecological niche may remain relatively unchanged over
119 time within closely related lineages (i.e., niche conservatism; Holt and Gaines 1992; Peterson *et al.* 1999),
120 which may be a key condition for the existence of allopatric distributions. Thus, during early stages of
121 divergence niche divergence would be minimal in a macrorefugia system, and divergence between
122 allopatric populations is expected to be primarily driven by drift. Natural selection could still be at play,
123 but its effects may not align with the refugia geographic dichotomy (i.e., divergence between isolated
124 regions), instead correlating with climatic conditions (Trujillo-Arias *et al.* 2020). A few studies of niche
125 evolution of birds in the Andean-Atlantic system support niche conservatism between recently evolved
126 taxa (Trujillo-Arias *et al.* 2018; Cabanne *et al.* 2019). A comparative study is needed to fully clarify the role
127 of niche divergence in diversification in macrorefugia systems.

128 Our goal was to address whether isolated forest biomes, like the Andean and the Atlantic forests,
129 act as a macrorefugia system promoting biological diversification (i.e., in complex morphological traits),
130 and to evaluate biogeographical hypotheses of their connection. Our questions are: 1) When and where
131 did forest corridors enable contact between these forest biomes? 2) Do the Andean and Atlantic forests
132 biomes act as a macrorefugia system? 3) What factors predict morphological diversification in a refugia
133 system?, and 4) Does niche divergence occur between disjunct populations in both forest realms?. To
134 answer these questions, we studied a sample of birds with disjunct populations in both forests, modeled
135 their ecological niches, projected them into past periods, and assessed connectivity between regions
136 based on predicted distributions. Subsequently, we tested whether species morphological variation is
137 predicted by factors such as geographic isolation between biomes, landscape resistance (current and
138 past), and/or climatic factors.

139

140 2. Materials and Methods

141 2.1. Samples selection and morphological data

142 To test for biological corridors and niche divergence between regions, we studied the following 24 bird
143 lineages with populations or species mostly restricted to both the Andean and Atlantic forests domains:
144 *Penelope obscura* (Temminck, 1815), *Tigrisoma fasciatum* (Such, 1825), *Parabuteo leucorrhous* (Quoy &
145 Gaimard, 1824), *Aegolius harrisii* (Cassin, 1849), *Amazona tucumana* (Cabanis, 1885)/ *A. pretrei*
146 (Temminck, 1830), *Batara cinerea* (Vieillot, 1819), *Thamnophilus ruficapillus* (Vieillot, 1816), *Chamaeza*

147 *campanisona* (Lichtenstein, MHK, 1823), *Lochmias nematura* (Lichtenstein, MHK, 1823), *Syndactyla*
148 *rufosuperciliata* (Lafresnaye, 1832), *Dendroma rufa* (Vieillot, 1818), *Phibalura flavirostris* (Vieillot, 1816),
149 *Laniisoma elegans* (Thunberg, 1823), *Platyrynchus mystaceus* (Vieillot, 1818), *Phylloscartes ventralis*
150 (Temminck, 1824), *Poecilotriccus plumbeiceps* (Lafresnaye, 1846), *Elaenia obscura* (d'Orbigny &
151 Lafresnaye, 1837), *Acrochordopus burmeisteri* (Cabanis & Heine, 1859), *Chlorophonia cyanocephala*
152 (Vieillot, 1819), *Chlorophonia cyanea* (Thunberg, 1822), *Arremon dorbignii* (Sclater, PL, 1856)/ *A.*
153 *flavirostris* (Swainson, 1838), *Cacicus chrysopterus* (Vigors, 1825), *Trichothraupis melanops* (Vieillot, 1818),
154 and *Pipraeidea melanonota* (Vieillot, 1819). Some of these lineages also had isolated populations in the
155 Guyanas region, Cerrado or Chaco, but none had a continuous distribution between the Andean and
156 Atlantic domains. All the studied lineages were single species (Clements *et al.* 2023), except in two pairs of
157 sister species, where each species was endemic to one of the two forests. This sample allowed examining
158 recent biogeographic processes between regions, as the differentiation levels between models were, at
159 most, at the species level, with relatively recent divergence (i.e., Pleistocene).

160 To evaluate the impact of climate and forest biogeographic region on morphological variation of
161 birds we restricted the study to the seven lineages with available population genetic data from previous
162 studies (Table 2). We studied a morphological dataset collected from 841 adult museum specimens of
163 both sexes (Fig. S1, Supplementary Information), from the ornithology collections of following museums:
164 American Museum of Natural History (USA); Burke Museum of Natural History (USA); Colección Boliviana
165 de Fauna (Bolivia); Museum of Vertebrate Zoology of the Cornell University (USA); Departamento de
166 Zoologia of the Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais (Brazil); Museo Argentino de Ciencias Naturales
167 Bernardino Rivadavia (Argentina); Museo de Historia Natural Noel Kempff Mercado (Bolivia); Museu de
168 Zoologia of the Universidade de São Paulo (Brazil) and Museu Paraense Emílio Goeldi (Brazil). From each
169 study skin, we studied the following six morphometric traits according to Baldwin *et al.* (1931): Bill length,
170 exposed culmen (BL); Bill length, from nostril (BLN); Bill width, culmen at nostril (BW); Bill height, at
171 nostrils (BH); Wing length (WL) and Tarsus length (TS). On each species, measurements were collected by
172 the same observer using a Mitutoyo caliper (accuracy of 0.05 mm). However, for *Syndactyla*
173 *rufosuperciliata* and *Trichothraupis melanops*, a small proportion of measurements was taken by a second
174 observer; thus, we included observer as a covariate in the statistical analyses. For some species, we used
175 morphometric data collected previously (Table 2). We imputed missing data with 'missForest' (Stekhoven
176 and Bühlmann 2012) for R 4.3.2 (R Core Team 2023).

177

178 2.2. Ecological niche models

179 We obtained ENMs of the 24 bird lineages. When a lineage consisted in two sister species, we built
180 independent ENMs for each species. Occurrence records were primarily obtained from the Global
181 Biodiversity Information Facility (<http://www.gbif.org/>), eBird (<http://www.ebird.org/>), Ecoregistros
182 (<http://www.ecoregistros.org/>), iNaturalist (<http://www.inaturalist.org/>) and Xeno-canto
183 (<http://www.xeno-canto.org/>). To complement records of species underrepresented in the previous
184 databases, we also included a limited number of records from Wikiaves (<http://www.wikiaves.com.br/>),
185 using locality to derive approximate coordinates. To avoid model overfitting, we filtered lineage data with
186 more than 100 occurrences by setting a thinning distance of 30 km, and lineages with less than 100
187 occurrences with a distance of 5 km. The final presence dataset comprised a total 7,485 records, varying
188 from 56 to 601 records per study model (see Table S1 for details).

189 We used the following five algorithms, in the package 'ENMTML' (Andrade *et al.* 2020) for R:
190 Generalized Additive Model (Hastie and Tibshirani 1986), Boosted Regression Tree (Friedman 2001),
191 Random Forest (Prasad *et al.* 2006), Support Vector Machine (Guo *et al.* 2005) and Maximum Entropy with
192 default features (Phillips *et al.* 2006). We built the ENMs with the current climatic variables from CHELSA
193 (Karger *et al.* 2017a, 2017b). Collinearity between climatic variables was controlled by estimating the
194 ENMs with the Principal Components of the climatic variables (De Marco and Nóbrega 2018), as
195 implemented in ENMTML with default settings. We evaluated model performance with the metrics: True
196 Skill Statistics (TSS), Area Under the Curve (AUC) and Kappa (Peterson *et al.* 2011). We projected the ENMs
197 into five paleoclimatic periods: mid-Holocene (MH, 8.326 — 4.2 ka, Fordham *et al.* 2017), early Holocene
198 (EH, 11.7 — 8.326 ka, Fordham *et al.* 2017), Heinrich Stadial 1 (HS1, 17.0 — 14.7 ka, Fordham *et al.* 2017),
199 Last Glacial Maximum (LGM, ca. 21 ka, Karger *et al.* 2017a, 2017b) and Last Interglacial (LI, ca. 130 ka,
200 Otto-Bliesner *et al.* 2006). All current and past climatic variables were downloaded from Paleoclim
201 (<http://www.paleoclim.org/>), with a resolution of 2.5 arc-min.

202 Ensemble ENMs were generated using a weighted mean based on TSS scores (Table S2). To
203 examine variation of lineage habitat range across periods, we generated binary maps by using the
204 threshold that maximized TSS (Allouche *et al.* 2006; see details in Supplementary Information). Then, we
205 calculated the number of suitable pixels as a proxy of lineage range. We applied a min-max normalization
206 to habitat suitability range to improve comparability between periods. Further methodological details
207 regarding ENMs are provided in Supplementary Information.

208

209 *2.3. Landscape connectivity analysis*

210 We used Circuitscape (McRae *et al.* 2013) to assess levels of landscape connectivity (Taylor *et al.* 1993;
211 McRae 2006) and to map corridors between Andean and Atlantic forests. We evaluated connectivity levels
212 by estimating landscape resistance distances, which describe the degree to which the landscape impedes
213 movement among patches, and thus the cost of dispersing across landscape elements (Taylor *et al.* 1993;
214 McRae 2006). To map corridors between forests, we generated connectivity maps indicating the most
215 suitable routes for bird movement between regions. Given the extensive latitudinal range of the study
216 area, we determined the latitudinal midpoints and divided the shapes of the two biomes—Andean and
217 Atlantic forests (as defined by Dinerstein *et al.* 2017)—into northern and southern sections. We then
218 estimated current distribution mass centers of each lineage and forest section (i.e., northern and
219 southern, see further details in Supplementary Information). We used Circuitscape in pairwise mode to
220 estimate resistance distances (and its reciprocal, the conductance) and connectivity maps, between mass
221 centers within latitudinal sections of both the Andean and Atlantic forests. We conducted Circuitscape
222 analysis for each lineage and studied periods, and summed individual connectivity maps to generate a final
223 cumulative connectivity map per period in QGIS v3.24.3 (QGIS Development Team 2024).

224 We conducted an Extended Phylogenetic ANOVA (Adams and Collyer 2024) to evaluate the impact
225 of time period and route of contact on modeled area (i.e., number of pixels) and conductance of Andean
226 and Atlantic forests birds. We conducted this analysis with function `extended.pgls` of ‘geomorph’ v4.0.10
227 for R (Baken *et al.* 2021; Adams *et al.* 2025), and with the `anova` function of R base. For this analysis, we
228 pruned the phylogeny of birds from Jetz *et al.* (2012) to allow representation of the 24 studied lineages.
229 When a studied taxon was not represented in the phylogeny of Jetz *et al.* (2012), we used the closest
230 available species based on the phylogeny.

231

232 *2.4. Impact of isolation and climate on morphological variation*

233 We conducted multiple matrix regression with randomization analyses (MMRR; Wang 2013) in a sample of
234 seven bird species to investigate the association between pairwise morphological variation and predictors
235 of biogeographic region, climate, and current and historical landscape resistance. We conducted separate
236 analyses for the independent variables bill, wing (Wing) and tarsus (Tarsus). For bill, we reduced data
237 variability with PCA and ran the analysis on the principal components with eigenvalues greater than one

238 (PC1_Bill and PC2_Bill) as obtained with 'psych' for R (Revelle 2024; see Supplementary Information and
239 Table S5).

240 A first independent metric (Biog_reg) consisted in an indicator of biogeographic region (Andes and
241 Atlantic realms). Samples located between the biogeographic regions - as defined in Figure 1- were
242 assigned as belonging to the same biogeographic region as the nearest sample. As climate independent
243 metrics we evaluated two sets of Bioclim variables: 1) metrics related to current temperature (bio 1 — 11),
244 and 2) metrics related to current precipitation (bio 12 — 19). We reduced variability of these variables
245 with PCA analysis and adopted the first two components for the MMRR analysis (PC1_{Temp} and PC2_{Temp} for
246 temperature variation, and PC1_{Prec} and PC2_{Prec} related to precipitation variation). To test the impact of
247 landscape configuration and permeability to potential dispersal and morphological variation, we
248 conducted a connectivity analysis in pairwise mode in Circuitscape. For each species, we obtained
249 resistance distances between all specimens' locations for the current (R_{CUR}) and past periods (R_{PAST}). To
250 obtain R_{PAST} , we averaged resistance across past periods. To control for potential confounding effects, we
251 also included indicators of genetic lineage (Gen) (see Extended Methods and Fig. S2 in Supplementary
252 Information), sex (Sex) and observer (Obs) as covariates. See further methodological explanation in
253 Supplementary Information.

254 To run the MMRR analyses, we used pairwise distances matrices between individuals for both the
255 dependent and independent metrics (except resistance metrics) by estimating differences between
256 observations. For quantitative variables (e.g., morphological response variables or PCs of climate
257 variables), distances were simply the differences between the two values. For categorical variables (e.g.,
258 Bio_reg or Sex), we assigned a value of 0 when two individuals shared the same category and 1 when they
259 differed. Before analyses, all variables (response and predictors) were standardized by centering (i.e.,
260 subtracting the mean) and scaling (i.e., dividing by the standard deviation). The MMRR R function (Wang
261 2013) was run using 1,000 permutations to estimate significance.

262

263 *2.5. Niche divergence analysis*

264 We conducted niche identity and background tests (Warren *et al.* 2008) to evaluate niche divergence
265 between populations or lineages restricted to the Andean and Atlantic forests domains. We followed
266 Broennimann *et al.* (2012) to apply these tests according to the PCA-environmental ordination method.
267 The identity test assumes as a null hypothesis that the compared populations occupy identical niches. The

268 test's statistics is D (Schoener 1970), a measure of niche overlap between two populations (D=1 full
269 overlap, D=0 no overlap at all). In the test, the observed D is compared with a null distribution of D
270 obtained by permutation to determine if the observed D is significantly lower, higher or similar to the null
271 hypothesis. To obtain the null distribution of D, occurrences of both empirical populations are randomly
272 reassigned across two simulated populations. The background test, on the other hand, accounts for the
273 available environment of each population. It does so by estimating D using random points drawn from the
274 available habitat in the range of one population while keeping the occurrences of the other population
275 intact. This procedure is repeated in both directions, yielding two frequency distributions for the
276 comparison.

277 To explore niche divergence through time, we also explored the association between niche
278 overlap (D) and divergence time between disjunct populations or lineages from the Andean and Atlantic
279 forests. Divergence times between disjunct populations or lineages were obtained from the literature
280 (Rocha *et al.* 2014; Trujillo-Arias *et al.* 2017, 2018, 2020; Bolívar-Leguizamón and Silveira 2019; Cabanne *et*
281 *al.* 2019; Lavinia *et al.* 2019; Bocalini *et al.* 2021; Bolívar-Leguizamón *et al.* 2024; Vázquez-López *et al.*
282 2024). The dataset used in this test is provided in Table S8.

283

284 3. Results

285 3.1. Ecological niche models

286 The ENMs of the 24 studied bird lineages exhibited strong predictive performance (i.e., all AUC values >
287 0.77, Mean AUC = 0.95, SD = 0.04; all TSS values > 0.41, Mean TSS = 0.82, SD = 0.11; Table S2). At the
288 community level, the models predicted a significant expansion of suitable habitat ranges during glacial
289 periods (HS1 and LGM; Fig. 2A), with Period accounting for 87.3% of the variation in modeled range (Table
290 1). The Present period showed the lowest mean range, whereas HS1 and LGM exhibited the largest
291 increases in suitable areas respect to Present (145% and 132% mean increases, respectively, Table S3).

292

293 3.2. Connectivity analysis between Andean and Atlantic forests

294 The Circuitscape analysis indicated significant higher connectivity between the Andean and Atlantic forests
295 during glacial periods (HS1 and LGM, Fig. 2B, and see Table S4 for the actual resistance values). About

296 44.9% of the variation in conductance among lineages was jointly predicted by time period and modeled
297 route (Table 1).

298 Across periods and lineages, the connectivity analysis described a persistent corridor between the
299 Andean and Atlantic forest through the CCT region (Fig. 3), along with higher conductance values for the
300 southern route (Fig. 2B). A single lineage deviated from the general pattern of connection through the
301 southern route. Particularly, *Platyrinchus mystaceus* presented in all periods greater connectivity through
302 the northern path (Table S4).

303 In addition to the primary route between the Andean and Atlantic forests identified at the CCT
304 region, our results suggested other complementary connections between these forests (Fig. 3). For
305 instance, one of these routes extended through central Chaco and was more pronounced during
306 interglacial periods (i.e., Present and Last Interglacial), while another route was located in central and
307 northern Cerrado, where connectivity increased substantially during glacial periods (LGM and Heinrich
308 Stadial 1). Interestingly, the central Cerrado route was only robust during the LGM.

309

310 *3.3. Predictors of morphological variation of birds*

311 The MMRR analyses indicated that morphological variation of Andean and Atlantic forests birds is mostly
312 explained by biogeographic region, climate and sex dimorphism (Table 2), although with weak power.
313 Biogeographic region and sex dimorphism were the most frequent predictors, appearing in 56.2% and
314 62.5% of all significant models across lineages and traits, respectively. Genetic lineage was excluded in
315 81.3% of the significant models and landscape resistance distances in 87.5%, making them the most
316 frequently removed variables, due to genetic lineage correlated with biogeographic region, while the two
317 landscape resistance distance metrics correlated with each other and biogeographic region.

318

319 *3.4. Niche divergence between Andean and Atlantic regions*

320 Our results indicated that disjunct bird populations in the Andean and Atlantic regions occupy distinct
321 climatic niches, while showing partial conservation of niche characteristics. First, niche overlap between
322 these populations and lineages was in average low (mean $D = 0.13$, $SD = 0.07$, $n=24$; Fig. 4), with the
323 identity test indicating that none of the niches compared between the Andean and Atlantic regions were
324 equivalent ($p < 0.05$, Table S7). Second, the background tests indicated that none of the populations

325 presented niche divergence between these forests that was higher than expected by chance and
326 background divergence (Fig. 4, result type LTC: 0%). The tests yielded a high proportion of no divergence
327 (result type NS >50%) and of niche conservatism (result type HTC > 20.8%).

328 Additionally, we found no association between niche overlap D (average D = 0.148, SD = 0.08, n =
329 13) and divergence time (average divergence = 1 Ma, SD = 0.65, n = 13, Table S8) between allopatric
330 populations or lineages from the Andes and the Atlantic realms (beta = -0.31, p = 0.299; Supplementary
331 Information), which is compatible with niche conservatism through time.

332

333 4. Discussion

334 We studied biogeographical connections and morphological evolution of birds between forest
335 macrorefugia. Our findings support that the Andean and Atlantic forests function as a macrorefugia
336 system driving biological diversification. Geographic isolation and climate divergence significantly
337 influenced morphological variation in rainforest birds. Late Pleistocene biogeographical connections
338 between these forests occurred during glacial periods, primarily via the southern Cerrado and its transition
339 to the Chaco. Additionally, niche conservatism among bird populations and lineages in these macrorefugia
340 suggests a limited role of ecological factors in driving evolutionary divergence between regions.

341

342 4.1. Andean and Atlantic forests as dynamic biomes

343 Our study provided evidence that the Andean and Atlantic forests are dynamic biomes. Ecological niche
344 models indicated synchronous range fluctuations for most studied bird lineages, with larger ranges during
345 glacial periods (i.e., HS1 and LGM, Table 1, Fig. 2A). Additionally, most studied lineages exhibited a
346 tendency of higher conductance between forests during glacial stages, particularly in the southern study
347 region (Table 1, Fig. 2B). These results supported that rainforest corridors expanded primarily during
348 glacial periods, allowing for potential connections between forest domains.

349 The range dynamism observed in the Andean and Atlantic forests birds align with studies
350 proposing that Quaternary glacial cycles shaped South American biome and that these forests functioned
351 as a refugia system driving biological diversification (Cabanne *et al.* 2016, 2019; Trujillo-Arias *et al.* 2017,
352 2018, 2020). Furthermore, a general trend of expansion of humid forest during glacial periods aligns with
353 niche modeling of animals and plants (Cabanne *et al.* 2016; Leite *et al.* 2016; Vergara *et al.* 2017; Trujillo-

354 Arias *et al.* 2020; Vasconcellos *et al.* 2024), of forest biomes (Sobral-Souza *et al.* 2015), and geological
355 evidence (Cruz *et al.* 2007; Deininger *et al.* 2019). This pattern contrasts with the traditional refugia model,
356 which assumes maximum forest fragmentation during glaciations (Haffer 1969). However, pronounced
357 cold global intervals (i.e., Heinrich Events) were associated in South America to extreme precipitation
358 (Wang *et al.* 2004; Smith and Rodbell 2010; Baker *et al.* 2020), which could have promoted expansion of
359 humid forests and high connectivity in forest organisms. During the Last Glacial Maximum, South America
360 experienced a complex precipitation pattern, including both drier and wetter areas, exemplified by the
361 Amazon's west-east precipitation dipole (Cheng *et al.* 2013; Baker and Fritz 2015; Berman *et al.* 2016;
362 Wang *et al.* 2017). Considering the cyclic nature of Quaternary climate, and that during glacial periods
363 certain areas were more humid than today, glacial cycles could have allowed changes in the distribution of
364 rainforests and hence cyclic connections between them.

365

366 4.2. The Cerrado as a contact region between the Andes and the Atlantic Forest

367 Our results supported that the Cerrado, rather than the Chaco, was the primary region where forest
368 corridors expanded during glacial periods, facilitating dispersal between the Andean and Atlantic forests.
369 The most stable corridor likely existed in the CCT zone, which showed the highest current flow across all
370 periods analyzed (Fig. 3). During higher connectivity periods (i.e., glacial stages), other parts of the Cerrado
371 beyond the CCT also became available for forest species dispersal (Fig. 3). In contrast, during periods of
372 reduced connectivity (i.e., interglacial stages), the CCT corridor remained suitable, while other potential
373 corridors in central Chaco, south of the Pilcomayo and Bermejo rivers, may have emerged. However, the
374 lower conductance observed along both northern and southern routes during interglacial stages (Fig. 2B,
375 Table S4) suggests that climatic conditions were less favorable for continuous forest corridor formation
376 compared to glacial periods.

377 Our results provided limited evidence for a northern South America connection between the
378 Andes and the Atlantic Forest, with humid forest expansions in the Caatinga (as raised for Amazon-Atlantic
379 past connections; Willis 1992; Batalha-Filho *et al.* 2013; Machado *et al.* 2021), and with a leading role of
380 the Guiana Shield, except during the HS1 (Fig. 3). In contrast, during periods with the strongest connection
381 between regions, the southern CCT connection was consistently the most established (Fig. 3). For species
382 showing similar connectivity in both northern and southern regions, the southern path remained stable
383 across periods, while the northern route varied. During HS1, a southwestern Amazonian path appeared,
384 merging with the southern route in the southern Cerrado, suggesting potential Amazon Basin connections.

385 In contrast, during the LGM, southern Amazonia and the central Cerrado gained importance relative to the
386 CCT.

387 A main Cerrado connection through the CCT during glacial periods was previously proposed by
388 Trujillo-Arias *et al.* (2020) based on genetic and niche analysis of birds. Other studies also suggest past
389 rainforest presence in the area (Ledru 1993) and propose similar hypotheses for the Atlantic-Amazon
390 system, supported by palynological, genetic and niche studies (Batalha-Filho *et al.* 2013; Ledo and Colli
391 2017). Our findings align with Trujillo-Arias *et al.* (2017), emphasizing the importance of the Chiquitano
392 Forest region and the Chapare buttress in the CCT connection between Andean and Atlantic forests.
393 Located in the western CCT (Bolivia), these regions separate the Amazon and the Paraná basin (Lundberg
394 *et al.* 1998) and are associated to high current flow in the connectivity analysis (Fig. 3). Furthermore, the
395 Chiquitano Forest has been proposed as a key contact zone between highland and lowland bird
396 populations (Remsen *et al.* 1991), highlighting its role in bridging biomes. Similarly, the Chapare buttress,
397 an antique contact zone between the central Andes and the western Brazilian Shield, may have acted as a
398 corridor between east-west taxa when the Miocene seas dominated the region (Prates *et al.* 2017).

399 Despite the support for a Chaco connection given by other studies based on niche models
400 (Turchetto-Zolet *et al.* 2016; Vergara *et al.* 2017), as well as by this study as a minor route for certain
401 species (Fig. 3), genetic data of birds do not support this hypothesis (Cabanne *et al.* 2019). This
402 discrepancy may arise from reproductive isolation being established before Chaco corridors formed, or
403 because, despite providing structural connections, the Chaco offered conditions insufficient for true
404 dispersal. Another factor could be barriers within the corridor, such as the Paraguay-Paraná rivers, which
405 are known to limit gene flow in bird taxa (Campagna *et al.* 2014; Kopuchian *et al.* 2020; Trujillo-Arias *et al.*
406 2020).

407 Biogeographic connections between the Andes and the Atlantic domains, occurring through
408 different regions than those exposed here, may have taken place during periods not evaluated in this
409 study (i.e., potentially older than the late Pleistocene). For example, within the Genus of passerines
410 *Scytalopus*, divergence between clades restricted to either the Andes and or to the Atlantic forests dates
411 back even further, to the late Miocene (Cadena *et al.* 2020). The landscape configuration and regions that
412 allowed the current distribution of this group remain unknown.

413

414 4.3. Isolation in macrorefugia and climate factors predict phenotypic divergence

415 Our results indicate that both population isolation and climatic factors are key predictors of intraspecific
416 morphological variation in birds from the Andean and Atlantic domains, reinforcing the role of these
417 forests as a macrorefugia system driving organic diversification. According to the MMRR results (Table 2),
418 biogeographic region (i.e., Andean or Atlantic) and landscape resistance predicted morphological variation
419 in many bird lineages, indicating the influence of geographic isolation on their diversification. For instance,
420 biogeographic region predicted at least one trait variation in 71.4% of the lineages and was the sole
421 predictor of a trait (PC1_Bill) for one case (i.e., species pair *Arremon dorbignii* and *A. flavirostris*). In
422 addition, landscape resistance accounted for variation in at least a trait in 42.8% of the studied lineages.

423 We also found that climatic metrics predicted morphological variation, consistent with action of
424 natural selection linked to these factors. Climatic metrics predicted variation in at least one trait in 57.14%
425 of the studied lineages, and were the sole predictor of a single trait (PC1_Bill) in one case (*Phylloscartes*
426 *ventralis*). Notably, in one lineage (14%), morphological variation was accounted for by solely sexual
427 dimorphism. Finally, both biogeographic region and climate factors jointly predicted variation of at least
428 one trait in 42.8% of the lineages, with no single factor showing clear dominance.

429 There was considerable variation in predictors of single traits variation. For instance, bill
430 morphology was affected by biogeographic region and climatic predictors in 71.4 % of the studied
431 lineages, while wing length was often explained by sex dimorphism, with a preponderant effect in also
432 71.4 % of the lineages (Table 2), with minimal impact of biogeographic region and climate predictors.
433 Tarsus variation was only predicted in 50% of the lineages, but with complex and weak models.

434 Our findings are consistent with previous studies in this forest system. For instance, *Phylloscartes*
435 *ventralis* and *Pipraeidea melanonota* showed no effect of biogeographic region on morphological
436 characters. They also exhibited the highest conductance values during glacial periods in the connectivity
437 analysis (Fig. 3, Table S4), suggesting high dispersal and recent divergence between isolated populations.
438 This is consistent with studies reporting low genetic differentiation and high gene flow between Andean
439 and Atlantic disjunct populations of these species (Lavinia *et al.* 2019; Trujillo-Arias *et al.* 2020).
440 Conversely, *Syndactyla rufosuperciliata* presented a strong effect of biogeographic region, consistent with
441 genetic analyses indicating a strong phylogeographic gap between the Andes and Atlantic forest (Cabanne
442 *et al.* 2019).

443 We found a negative relationship between bill variation of *Poecilotriccus plumbeiceps* and
444 biogeographic region transition (Table 2), evidencing that geographic isolation has had a low impact on
445 this trait. Instead, climate factors had a greater impact on bill and tarsus length than the biogeographic

446 region transition, as shown by the regression coefficient comparisons. This aligns with our previous study
447 of this species, which detected a north-south morphological cline in both the Atlantic and Andean regions
448 (Trujillo-Arias *et al.* 2020), rather than a morphological gap between forests, as could have been predicted
449 according to the refugia model. Such a pattern of morphological variation between disjunct lineages may
450 reflect parallel adaptation to local climate conditions and or phenotypic plasticity (Zamudio *et al.* 2016;
451 Trujillo-Arias *et al.* 2020). Additionally, *P. plumbeiceps* exhibited low landscape conductance (Table S4),
452 suggesting no recent contact between populations and further supporting the lack of gene flow between
453 Andean and Atlantic populations (Trujillo-Arias *et al.* 2020).

454 Notably, *Arremon dorbignii/A. flavirostris* was the only lineage where geographic factors alone
455 explained morphological variation of a trait (PC1_Bill), likely reflecting strong isolation. This study case was
456 the only one considering two sister lineages that are clear species (but see Cavarzere *et al.* 2024), with
457 divergence in song, morphology and genetic, and a temporal separation of 0.85 — 2 Ma (Buainain *et al.*
458 2016, 2022; Trujillo-Arias *et al.* 2017). However, the low coefficient of determination for the biogeographic
459 region transition suggests that additional factors beyond isolation are impacting divergence in this lineage.

460 Wing length, often used as a proxy for body size (Hamilton 1961; Ashton 2002), was the only trait
461 consistently affected by sexual dimorphism across most lineages (Table 2), with males having the largest
462 wings. These results are in agreement with previous studies indicating the impact of sexual dimorphism on
463 wing length (Cueto *et al.* 2015; Maccarone and Brzorad 2016; García Antón *et al.* 2018).

464 The morphological variation between the Andes and the Atlantic forests lineages was weakly
465 explained by our models, as indicated by the relatively low regression coefficients for Bio_reg (Table 2).
466 The shallow morphological divergence between these populations and lineages aligns with previous
467 studies that found phenotypic differences between allopatric populations primarily in plumage, with
468 idiosyncratic changes and minimal, though constant, variation in morphometric traits (Winger and Bates
469 2015; Buainain *et al.* 2016; Cavarzere *et al.* 2024). This pattern of low morphological divergence contrasts
470 with the strong phylogeographic breaks observed between Andean and Atlantic populations of the studied
471 species (Trujillo-Arias *et al.* 2017, 2018, 2020; Cabanne *et al.* 2019; Lavinia *et al.* 2019), suggesting that
472 phenotypic variation may lag behind genetic divergence. The low morphological divergence may indicate
473 some degree of balancing or parallel selection between isolated regions, potentially linked to the relatively
474 conserved habitats occupied by these populations and lineages (Trujillo-Arias *et al.* 2020; this study).

475

476 *4.4. Niche evolution in a macrorefugia system.*

477 We found no evidence of strong niche divergence between bird populations distributed between the
478 Andean and Atlantic forests. While the identity test indicated that niches were not equivalent between
479 isolated forest domains, the background test revealed that, in some lineages, niches did not deviate from
480 what would be expected based on climatic differences between these forests, or that in others niche
481 overlap was higher than expected (Fig. 4), indicating niche conservatism in all cases (Peterson 2011).
482 Additionally, the lack of association between niche overlap (Schoener's D) and divergence time between
483 disjunct populations or lineages in the Andes and Atlantic regions further supported a trend of niche
484 conservatism in the macrorefugia system (see Extended Results in Supplementary Information).

485 According to Peterson (2011), the identity test may detect real but biologically non-significant
486 differences in the ecological niche. The findings of background test of greater-than-expected niche overlap
487 in many lineages suggests that species tend to occupy sites with similar niche conditions across isolated
488 forests, despite differing environmental availabilities. However, in more than half of the studied lineages,
489 this pattern was absent, indicating niche occupancy consistent with environmental availability in each
490 region.

491 The results of the background test varied depending on the direction of comparison (Fig. 4). For
492 instance, 20.8% of the studied lineages exhibited a D higher than expected by chance when comparing the
493 observed Atlantic niches with simulated Andean niches (background), while in the opposite direction 50%
494 of the lineages presented the same result type. This asymmetry (i.e., 20.8% vs 50 %) in the result type
495 proportion highlights climatic differences between the Andean and Atlantic forests. The Andean forests,
496 with their extensive altitudinal gradient, encompass a wider and more heterogeneous range of
497 environmental conditions, leading to broader observed and available niches in climatic space. This broader
498 niche space increases the likelihood of overlap with more restricted climatic niches of the Atlantic Forest
499 populations. In contrast, the Atlantic Forest occupies a much narrower climatic space, both in observed
500 and available niches. As a result, when niches are randomized within this constrained background, the
501 probability of exceeding observed Schoener's D values remains low. These finding suggests that
502 populations in the Atlantic Forest are more tightly constrained by local climatic conditions, whereas
503 Andean populations exhibit greater ecological flexibility, likely reflecting adaptation to a broader range of
504 environmental conditions.

505 These niche analysis results are concordant with studies supporting that niche divergence tend to
506 be lower in allopatric sister species or populations of the same species than in sympatric or parapatric

507 situations (McCormack *et al.* 2010; Pitteloud *et al.* 2017). In allopatry, niche conservatism can prevent
508 adaptation to the suboptimal conditions of geographical barriers, while in sympatry/parapatry evolution
509 occurs through differential adaptation in the same or adjacent geographic ranges leading to reproductive
510 isolation and niche divergence (Wiens and Graham 2005).

511 Niche conservatism may delay phenotypic divergence between macrorefugia in the early stages of
512 evolution. We suggested earlier that the low levels of morphological divergence that we observed
513 between disjunct populations and lineages from the Andes and Atlantic regions may indicate balancing or
514 parallel selection, possible linked to their occupancy of similar habitats and niches (Trujillo-Arias *et al.*
515 2020). Longer divergence times than the average in our study sample (average= 1 Ma, Table S8) may be
516 necessary to detect strong morphological modifications between isolated populations in similar
517 environments. Our results suggest that disjunct populations of lineages shared by the Andean and Atlantic
518 forests domains are in their early stages of divergence, where most isolated populations exhibit clear
519 phylogeographic gaps (Trujillo-Arias *et al.* 2017, 2018, 2020; Cabanne *et al.* 2019; Lavinia *et al.* 2019) but
520 relative similar phenotypes due to occupying similar—but not identical—niches.

521

522 **Conclusions**

523 Our study highlighted the role of macrorefugia systems in the evolution of South American biota. We
524 provided evidence that wet forest expansions primarily occurred during glacial periods, particularly in the
525 Cerrado region, with a persistent corridor in the Cerrado–Chaco transition likely facilitating contact
526 between the Andes and Atlantic forests. Pleistocene climate oscillations enabled inter-forest connections
527 while maintaining regional differentiation. Evolution between macrorefugia likely involved sporadic gene
528 flow during expansion periods, followed by allopatric divergence driven by drift and local adaptation.
529 However, local adaptation may have influenced some species' trait variation patterns aligned with
530 environmental gradients within refugia, rather than macrorefugia geographic transitions.

531 Finally, we observed niche conservatism among disjunct populations and lineages, suggesting it
532 may delay phenotypic divergence between macrorefugia. This observation aligns with the idea that
533 divergence progresses more slowly in similar environments than in distinct ones (Price 2008).

534

535 **Acknowledgments**

536 We thank the staff and curators of all the institutions that granted access to their specimen collections.
537 This study was funded by the Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Tecnológicas of Argentina
538 (PhD and Post Doc scholarship to B.R.D. and C.A.L.R., respectively, and grants PIP 2015 0637 and PIP 2020
539 3168), and the Agencia Nacional de Promoción Científica y Tecnológica of Argentina (grants PICT 2014
540 2154, 2018-02689 and 2020-03796). V.C. thanks Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível
541 Superior of Brazil and Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de São Paulo (grant 2010/11798-5).

542

543 **Credit Statement**

544 Bárbara R. Delgado (contributed to study conception, collected data, performed analyses and wrote the
545 manuscript), Alejandro M. Ferreiro (contributed substantially to revisions), Natalia Trujillo-Arias
546 (contributed to study conception and collected data), Nelson Buainain (collected data), Luís F. Silveira
547 (collected data), Cássia A. Lima Rezende (collected data), Vagner Cavarzere (collected data) and Gustavo S.
548 Cabanne (contributed to study conception, collected data, performed analyses and wrote the manuscript).

549

550 **Supplementary Data**

551 Supplementary data are available at the *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society* online site.

552 Supplementary Information: Extended Methods and Results, Figures (S1 – S3) and Tables (S1 – S8).

553

554 **Conflict of Interest**

555 The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

556

557 **Data Availability Statement**

558 The datasets and scripts used in this work are available at the GitHub repository
559 <https://github.com/barbaradel/Connectivity-and-evolution-between-forest-macrorefugia>.

560

561 **References**

- 562 Adams DC, Collyer ML. Extending phylogenetic regression models for comparing within-species patterns
563 across the tree of life. *Methods Ecol Evol* 2024;**15**:2234–46.
- 564 Adams DC, Collyer ML, Kaliontzopoulou A *et al.* Geomorph: Software for geometric morphometric
565 analyses. 2025.
- 566 Allouche O, Tsoar A, Kadmon R. Assessing the accuracy of species distribution models: prevalence, kappa
567 and the true skill statistic (TSS). *Journal of Applied Ecology* 2006;**43**:1223–32.
- 568 Andrade AFA de, Velazco SJE, De Marco Júnior P. ENMTML: An R package for a straightforward
569 construction of complex ecological niche models. *Environmental Modelling and Software* 2020;**125**,
570 DOI: 10.1016/j.envsoft.2019.104615.
- 571 Ashton KG. Patterns of within-species body size variation of birds: strong evidence for Bergmann’s rule.
572 *Global Ecology and Biogeography* 2002;**11**:505–23.
- 573 Avise JC. *Phylogeography: The History and Formation of Species*. Harvard University Press, 2000.
- 574 Baken EK, Collyer ML, Kaliontzopoulou A *et al.* geomorph v4.0 and gmShiny: Enhanced analytics and a new
575 graphical interface for a comprehensive morphometric experience. *Methods Ecol Evol* 2021;**12**:2355–
576 63.
- 577 Baker PA, Fritz SC. Nature and causes of Quaternary climate variation of tropical South America. *Quat Sci*
578 *Rev* 2015;**124**:31–47.
- 579 Baker PA, Fritz SC, Battisti DS *et al.* Beyond Refugia: New Insights on Quaternary Climate Variation and the
580 Evolution of Biotic Diversity in Tropical South America. In: Rull V, Carnaval AC (eds.), *Neotropical*
581 *Diversification: Patterns and Processes*. Springer Nature Switzerland, 2020, 51–70.
- 582 Baldwin SP, Oberholser HC, Worley LG *et al.* *Measurements of Birds*. Scientific Publications of the
583 Cleveland Museum of Natural History, 1931.
- 584 Batalha-Filho H, Fjeldså J, Fabre PH *et al.* Connections between the Atlantic and the Amazonian forest
585 avifaunas represent distinct historical events. *J Ornithol* 2013;**154**:41–50.
- 586 Berman AL, Silvestri GE, Tonello MS. Differences between Last Glacial Maximum and present-day
587 temperature and precipitation in southern South America. *Quat Sci Rev* 2016;**150**:221–33.
- 588 Bocalini F, Bolívar-Leguizamón SD, Silveira LF *et al.* Comparative phylogeographic and demographic
589 analyses reveal a congruent pattern of sister relationships between bird populations of the northern
590 and south-central Atlantic Forest. *Mol Phylogenet Evol* 2021;**154**:106973.
- 591 Bolívar-Leguizamón SD, Bocalini F, Silveira LF *et al.* The role of biogeographical barriers on the historical
592 dynamics of passerine birds with a circum-Amazonian distribution. *Ecol Evol* 2024;**14**:e10860.
- 593 Bolívar-Leguizamón SD, Silveira LF. Comparative phylogeography of Passerine birds with a circum-
594 Amazonian distribution. 2019.
- 595 Broennimann O, Fitzpatrick MC, Pearman PB *et al.* Measuring ecological niche overlap from occurrence
596 and spatial environmental data. *Global Ecology and Biogeography* 2012;**21**:481–97.

- 597 Buainain N, Brito GRR, Firme DH *et al.* Taxonomic revision of Saffron-billed Sparrow *Arremon flavirostris*
598 Swainson, 1838 (Aves: Passerellidae) with comments on its holotype and type locality. *Zootaxa*
599 2016;**4178**:547–67.
- 600 Buainain N, Ferreira M, Avendaño JE *et al.* Biogeography of a neotropical songbird radiation reveals similar
601 diversification dynamics between montane and lowland clades. *J Biogeogr* 2022;**49**:1260–73.
- 602 Bukowski B, Campagna L, Rodríguez-Cajarville MJ *et al.* The role of glaciations in the evolutionary history
603 of a widely distributed Neotropical open habitat bird. *JBiol* 2024;**51**:199–214.
- 604 Cabanne GS, Calderón L, Trujillo Arias N *et al.* Effects of Pleistocene climate changes on species ranges and
605 evolutionary processes in the Neotropical Atlantic Forest. *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society*
606 2016;**119**:856–72.
- 607 Cabanne GS, Campagna L, Trujillo-Arias N *et al.* Phylogeographic variation within the Buff-browed Foliage-
608 gleaner (Aves: Furnariidae: *Syndactyla rufosuperciliata*) supports an Andean-Atlantic forests
609 connection via the Cerrado. . *Mol Phylogenet Evol* 2019;**133**:198–213.
- 610 Cadena CD, Cuervo AM, Céspedes LN *et al.* Systematics, biogeography, and diversification of *Scytalopus*
611 *tapaculos* (Rhinocryptidae), an enigmatic radiation of Neotropical montane birds. *Auk* 2020;**137**, DOI:
612 10.1093/AUK/UKZ077.
- 613 Campagna L, Kopuchian C, Tubaro PL *et al.* Secondary contact followed by gene flow between divergent
614 mitochondrial lineages of a widespread Neotropical songbird (*Zonotrichia capensis*). *Biological*
615 *Journal of the Linnean Society* 2014;**111**:863–8.
- 616 Carnaval AC, Moritz C. Historical climate modelling predicts patterns of current biodiversity in the Brazilian
617 Atlantic forest. *J Biogeogr* 2008;**35**:1187–201.
- 618 Cavarzere V, Costa TV V., Cabanne GS *et al.* A new species of tanager (Aves: Thraupidae) from the Eastern
619 slopes of the Andes. *Zootaxa* 2024;**5468**:541–56.
- 620 Cheng H, Sinha A, Cruz FW *et al.* Climate change patterns in Amazonia and biodiversity. *Nature*
621 *Communications* 2013 4:1 2013;**4**:1–6.
- 622 Clements JF, Rasmussen PC, Schulenberg TS *et al.* The eBird/Clements checklist of Birds of the World:
623 v2023b. Downloaded from <https://www.birds.cornell.edu/clementschecklist/download/> 2023.
- 624 Cruz FW, Burns SJ, Jercinovic M *et al.* Evidence of rainfall variations in Southern Brazil from trace element
625 ratios (Mg/Ca and Sr/Ca) in a Late Pleistocene stalagmite. *Geochim Cosmochim Acta* 2007;**71**:2250–
626 63.
- 627 Cueto VR, Bravo SP, Trujillo-Arias N *et al.* Sex determination by morphometry of adult White-crested
628 Elaenia (*Elaenia albiceps chilensis*). *Revista Brasileira de Ornitologia* 2015 23:1 2015;**23**:18–24.
- 629 Deininger M, Ward BM, Novello VF *et al.* Late Quaternary Variations in the South American Monsoon
630 System as Inferred by Speleothems—New Perspectives Using the SISAL Database. *Quaternary* 2019,
631 *Vol 2, Page 6* 2019;**2**:6.

- 632 Delgado BR, Mogni VY, Trujillo-Arias N *et al.* Historia biogeográfica del Gran Chaco: modelado de nicho y
633 filogeografía de monterita cabeza negra (*Microspingus melanoleucus*) (Aves: Thraupidae).
634 2021;**36**:107–19.
- 635 Dinerstein E, Olson D, Joshi A *et al.* An Ecoregion-Based Approach to Protecting Half the Terrestrial Realm.
636 *Bioscience* 2017;**67**:534–45.
- 637 Erize F, Rodriguez Mata JR, Rumboll M. *Birds of South America - Non- Passerines: Rheas to Woodpeckers.*
638 Princeton, New York: Princeton University Press, 2006.
- 639 Ferreira AM, Pinotti JD, Poljak S *et al.* Effects of Quaternary climatic oscillations over the Chacoan fauna:
640 phylogeographic patterns in the southern three-banded armadillo *Tolypeutes matacus* (Cingulata:
641 Chlamyphoridae). *Zool J Linn Soc* 2024;**200**:825–36.
- 642 Fordham DA, Saltré F, Haythorne S *et al.* PaleoView: a tool for generating continuous climate projections
643 spanning the last 21 000 years at regional and global scales. *Ecography* 2017;**40**:1348–58.
- 644 Friedman JH. Greedy Function Approximation: A Gradient Boosting Machine. *The Annals of Statistics*
645 2001;**29**:1180–232.
- 646 García Antón A, Garza V, Traba J. Climate, isolation and intraspecific competition affect morphological
647 traits in an endangered steppe bird, the Dupont’s Lark *Chersophilus duponti*. *Bird Study*
648 2018;**65**:373–84.
- 649 Guo Q, Kelly M, Graham CH. Support vector machines for predicting distribution of Sudden Oak Death in
650 California. *Ecol Modell* 2005;**182**:75–90.
- 651 Haffer J. Speciation in amazonian forest birds. *Science (1979)* 1969;**165**:131–7.
- 652 Hamilton TH. The Adaptive Significances of Intraspecific Trends of Variation in Wing Length and Body Size
653 Among Bird Species. *Evolution (N Y)* 1961;**15**:180.
- 654 Van der Hammen T. The Pleistocene Changes of Vegetation and Climate in Tropical South America. *J*
655 *Biogeogr* 1974;**1**:3.
- 656 Hastie TJ, Tibshirani R. Generalized additive models. *Statistical models* 1986;**1**:297–318.
- 657 Holt RD, Gaines MS. Analysis of adaptation in heterogeneous landscapes: Implications for the evolution of
658 fundamental niches. *Evol Ecol* 1992;**6**:433–47.
- 659 Jetz W, Thomas GH, Joy JB *et al.* The global diversity of birds in space and time. *Nature* 2012 **491**:7424
660 2012;**491**:444–8.
- 661 Karger DN, Conrad O, Böhner J *et al.* Climatologies at high resolution for the earth’s land surface areas.
662 *Scientific Data* 2017 **4**:1 2017a;**4**:1–20.
- 663 Karger DN, Conrad O, Böhner J *et al.* *Data from: Climatologies at High Resolution for the Earth’s Land*
664 *Surface Areas.*, 2017b.
- 665 Kopuchian C, Campagna L, Lijtmaer DA *et al.* A test of the riverine barrier hypothesis in the largest
666 subtropical river basin in the Neotropics. *Mol Ecol* 2020;**29**:2137–49.

- 667 Lavinia PD, Barreira AS, Campagna L *et al.* Contrasting evolutionary histories in Neotropical birds:
668 Divergence across an environmental barrier in South America. *Mol Ecol* 2019;**28**:1730–47.
- 669 Ledo RMD, Colli GR. The historical connections between the Amazon and the Atlantic Forest revisited. *J*
670 *Biogeogr* 2017;**44**:2551–63.
- 671 Ledru MP. Late Quaternary Environmental and Climatic Changes in Central Brazil. *Quat Res* 1993;**39**:90–8.
- 672 Ledru MP, Martin L, Soubies F *et al.* Registro palinológico das variações climáticas no decorrer dos últimos
673 30.000 anos em sedimentos da lagoa campestre na Serra do Salitre, município de Patrocínio (MG).
674 *Publicação Especial N1 - Resumos* 1991:55–6.
- 675 Leite YLR, Costa LP, Loss AC *et al.* Neotropical forest expansion during the last glacial period challenges
676 refuge hypothesis. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 2016;**113**:1008–13.
- 677 Lundberg JG, Marshall LG, Guerrero J *et al.* The stage for neotropical fish diversification: A history of
678 tropical South American rivers. In: Malabarba LR, Reis EE, Vari RP, *et al.* (eds.), *Phylogeny and*
679 *Classification of Neotropical Fishes*. Vol 1. Edipucrs. Porto Alegre, 1998, 13–48.
- 680 Maccarone AD, Brzorad JN. Intraspecific and Intersexual Variation in Three Species of Wading Birds Using
681 Morphometric Measurements. <https://doi.org/101675/0630390212> 2016;**39**:205–8.
- 682 Machado AF, Ritter CD, Miranda CL *et al.* Potential mammalian species for investigating the past
683 connections between Amazonia and the Atlantic Forest. *PLoS One* 2021;**16**:e0250016.
- 684 De Marco PJ, Nóbrega CC. Evaluating collinearity effects on species distribution models: An approach
685 based on virtual species simulation. *PLoS One* 2018;**13**:e0202403.
- 686 McCormack JE, Zellmer AJ, Knowles LL. Does niche divergence accompany allopatric divergence in
687 *Aphelocoma* jays as predicted under ecological speciation?: insights from tests with niche models.
688 *Evolution (N Y)* 2010;**64**:1231–44.
- 689 McRae BH. Isolation by resistance. *Evolution (N Y)* 2006;**60**:1551–61.
- 690 McRae BH, Shah VB, Mohapatra TK. Circuitscape 4 User Guide. 2013.
- 691 Moritz C, Patton JL, Schneider CJ *et al.* Diversification of rainforest faunas: An integrated molecular
692 approach. *Annu Rev Ecol Syst* 2000;**31**:533–63.
- 693 Musher LJ, Galante PJ, Thom G *et al.* Shifting ecosystem connectivity during the Pleistocene drove
694 diversification and gene-flow in a species complex of Neotropical birds (Tityridae: Pachyramphus). *J*
695 *Biogeogr* 2020;**47**:1714–26.
- 696 Nores M. Bird Speciation in Subtropical South America in Relation to Forest Expansion and Retraction. *Auk*
697 1992;**109**:346–57.
- 698 Oliveira-Filho AT, Ratter JA. A study of the origin of central Brazilian forests by the analysis of plant species
699 distribution patterns. *Edinb J Bot* 1995;**52**:141–94.
- 700 Otto-Bliesner BL, Marshall SJ, Overpeck JT *et al.* Simulating arctic climate warmth and icefield retreat in
701 the last interglaciation. *Science (1979)* 2006;**311**:1751–3.

- 702 Papadopoulou A, Knowles LL. Toward a paradigm shift in comparative phylogeography driven by trait-
703 based hypotheses. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 2016;**113**:8018–24.
- 704 Patterson BD, Solari S, Velazco PM. The role of the Andes in the diversification and biogeography of
705 Neotropical mammals. In: Patterson BD, Costa LP (eds.), *Bones, Clones and Biomes: The History and*
706 *Geography of Recent Neotropical Mammals*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2012, 351–78.
- 707 Peterson AT. Ecological niche conservatism: a time-structured review of evidence. *J Biogeogr*
708 2011;**38**:817–27.
- 709 Peterson AT, Soberón J, Pearson RG *et al.* *Ecological Niches and Geographic Distributions*. Princeton, N.J.:
710 Princeton University Press, 2011.
- 711 Peterson AT, Soberón J, Sánchez-Cordero V. Conservatism of Ecological Niches in Evolutionary Time.
712 *Science (1979)* 1999;**285**:1265–7.
- 713 Phillips SB, Aneja VP, Kang D *et al.* Maximum entropy modeling of species geographic distributions. *Ecol*
714 *Modell* 2006;**190**:231–59.
- 715 Pitteloud C, Arrigo N, Suchan T *et al.* Climatic niche evolution is faster in sympatric than allopatric lineages
716 of the butterfly genus *Pyrgus*. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 2017;**284**, DOI:
717 10.1098/RSPB.2017.0208.
- 718 Prasad AM, Iverson LR, Liaw A. Newer classification and regression tree techniques: Bagging and random
719 forests for ecological prediction. *Ecosystems* 2006;**9**:181–99.
- 720 Prates I, Melo-Sampaio PR, Drummond L de O *et al.* Biogeographic links between southern Atlantic Forest
721 and western South America: Rediscovery, re-description, and phylogenetic relationships of two rare
722 montane anole lizards from Brazil. *Mol Phylogenet Evol* 2017;**113**:49–58.
- 723 Price T. *Speciation in Birds*. Roberts and Company, 2008.
- 724 QGIS Development Team. QGIS Geographic Information System. 2024.
- 725 R Core Team. R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing. 2023.
- 726 Remsen J V., Rocha O, Schmitt G *et al.* Zoogeography and Geographic Variation of *Platyrinchus Mystaceus*
727 in Bolivia and Peru, and the Circum-amazonian Distribution Pattern . *Ornitol Neotrop* 1991;**2**:77–83.
- 728 Revelle WR. *psych: Procedures for Personality and Psychological Research*. 2024.
- 729 Ribeiro V, Werneck FP, Machado RB. Distribution dynamics of South American savanna birds in response
730 to Quaternary climate change. *Austral Ecol* 2016;**41**:768–77.
- 731 Ridgely RS., Tudor Guy. *Field guide to the songbirds of South America : the passerines*. 2009:750.
- 732 Rocha A V., Rivera LO, Martinez J *et al.* Biogeography of speciation of two sister species of neotropical
733 amazona (Aves, Psittaciformes) Based on mitochondrial sequence data. *PLoS One* 2014;**9**, DOI:
734 10.1371/JOURNAL.PONE.0108096.
- 735 Rull V. Macrorefugia and microrefugia: A response to tzedakis *et al.* *Trends Ecol Evol* 2014;**29**:243–4.
- 736 Schoener TW. Nonsynchronous Spatial Overlap of Lizards in Patchy Habitats. *Ecology* 1970;**51**:408–18.

- 737 Sérsic AN, Cosacov A, Cocucci AA *et al.* Emerging phylogeographical patterns of plants and terrestrial
738 vertebrates from Patagonia. *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society* 2011;**103**:475–94.
- 739 Silva JMC da. Distribution of Amazonian and Atlantic Birds in Gallery Forests of the Cerrado Region, South
740 America. *Ornitol Neotrop* 1996;**7**:1–18.
- 741 Simpson Vuilleumier B. Pleistocene Changes in the Fauna and Flora of South America. *Science (1979)*
742 1971;**173**:771–80.
- 743 Smith JA, Rodbell DT. Cross-cutting moraines reveal evidence for North Atlantic influence on glaciers in the
744 tropical Andes. *J Quat Sci* 2010;**25**:243–8.
- 745 Sobral-Souza T, Lima-Ribeiro MS, Solferini VN. Biogeography of Neotropical Rainforests: past connections
746 between Amazon and Atlantic Forest detected by ecological niche modeling. *Evol Ecol* 2015;**29**:643–
747 55.
- 748 Stekhoven DJ, Bühlmann P. MissForest—non-parametric missing value imputation for mixed-type data.
749 *Bioinformatics* 2012;**28**:112–8.
- 750 Taylor PD, Fahrig L, Henein K *et al.* Connectivity is a vital element of landscape structure. *Oikos*
751 1993;**68**:571–3.
- 752 Trujillo-Arias N, Calderón L, Santos FR *et al.* Forest corridors between the central Andes and the southern
753 Atlantic Forest enabled dispersal and peripatric diversification without niche divergence in a
754 passerine. *Mol Phylogenet Evol* 2018;**128**:221–32.
- 755 Trujillo-Arias N, Dantas GPM, Arbeláez-Cortés E *et al.* The niche and phylogeography of a passerine reveal
756 the history of biological diversification between the Andean and the Atlantic forests. *Mol Phylogenet*
757 *Evol* 2017;**112**:107–21.
- 758 Trujillo-Arias N, Rodríguez-Cajarville MJ, Sari E *et al.* Evolution between forest macrorefugia is linked to
759 discordance between genetic and morphological variation in Neotropical passerines. *Mol Phylogenet*
760 *Evol* 2020;**149**, DOI: 10.1016/j.ympev.2020.106849.
- 761 Turchetto-Zolet AC, Salgueiro F, Turchetto C *et al.* Phylogeography and ecological niche modelling in
762 *Eugenia uniflora* (Myrtaceae) suggest distinct vegetational responses to climate change between the
763 southern and the northern Atlantic Forest. *Botanical Journal of the Linnean Society* 2016;**182**:670–88.
- 764 Vanzolini P, Williams E. South American anoles: the geographic differentiation and evolution of the anolis
765 *Chrysolepis* species group (Sauria, Iguanidae). *Arq Zool* 1970;**19**:125–298.
- 766 Vasconcellos MM, Varela S, Reginato M *et al.* Evaluating the impact of historical climate and early human
767 groups in the Araucaria Forest of eastern South America. *Ecography* 2024;**2024**:e06756.
- 768 Vázquez-López M, Ramírez-Barrera SM, Terrones-Ramírez AK *et al.* Biogeographic factors contributing to
769 the diversification of Euphoniinae (Aves, Passeriformes, Fringillidae): a phylogenetic and ancestral
770 areas analysis. *Zookeys* 2024;**1188**:169.
- 771 Vergara J, Acosta LE, González-Ittig RE *et al.* The disjunct pattern of the Neotropical harvestman
772 *Discocyrtus dilatatus* (Gonyleptidae) explained by climate-driven range shifts in the Quaternary:
773 Paleodistributional and molecular evidence. *PLoS One* 2017;**12**:e0187983.

- 774 Wang IJ. Examining the full effects of landscape heterogeneity on spatial genetic variation: A multiple
775 matrix regression approach for quantifying geographic and ecological isolation. *Evolution (N Y)*
776 2013;**67**:3403–11.
- 777 Wang X, Auler AS, Edwards LL *et al.* Wet periods in northeastern Brazil over the past 210 kyr linked to
778 distant climate anomalies. *Nature 2004 432:7018* 2004;**432**:740–3.
- 779 Wang X, Edwards RL, Auler AS *et al.* Hydroclimate changes across the Amazon lowlands over the past
780 45,000 years. *Nature 2017 541:7636* 2017;**541**:204–7.
- 781 Warren DL, Glor RE, Turelli M. Environmental niche equivalency versus conservatism: quantitative
782 approaches to niche evolution. *Evolution (N Y)* 2008;**62**:2868–83.
- 783 Wickham H. *Ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis*. New York: Springer-Verlag New York, 2016.
- 784 Wiens JJ, Graham CH. Niche conservatism: Integrating evolution, ecology, and conservation biology. *Annu*
785 *Rev Ecol Evol Syst* 2005;**36**:519–39.
- 786 Willis EO. Zoogeographical origins of eastern Brazilian birds. *Ornitol Neotrop* 1992;**1**:1.
- 787 Winger BM, Bates JM. The tempo of trait divergence in geographic isolation: Avian speciation across the
788 Marañón Valley of Peru. *Evolution (N Y)* 2015;**69**:772–87.
- 789 Wüster W, Ferguson JE, Quijada-Mascareñas JA *et al.* Tracing an invasion: landbridges, refugia, and the
790 phylogeography of the Neotropical rattlesnake (Serpentes: Viperidae: *Crotalus durissus*). *Mol Ecol*
791 2005;**14**:1095–108.
- 792 Zamudio KR, Bell RC, Mason NA. Phenotypes in phylogeography: Species' traits, environmental variation,
793 and vertebrate diversification. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 2016;**113**:8041–8.
- 794 Zurita AE, Miño-Boilini ÁR, Francia A *et al.* Paleontología y cronología del Cuaternario de las provincias de
795 Corrientes y Formosa, Argentina. *Acta geológica lilloana* 2014;**26**:75–86.
- 796
- 797

Table 1. Extended Phylogenetic ANOVA to evaluate impact of period and route of contact on modeled range area and conductance of Andean and Atlantic forests bird lineages. Df: degrees of freedom. SS: sum of square. MS: mean square. R²: coefficient of determination.

Source of variation	Df	SS	MS	R ²	F-statistic	p-value
Dependant metric: Range area						
Period	5	3.507×10^{12}	7.014×10^{11}	0.873	188.940	<0.001
Residuals	138	5.123×10^{11}	3.712×10^9	0.127		
Total	143	4.019×10^{12}				
Dependant metric: Conductance						
Period	5	0.719	0.144	0.287	29.269	<0.001
Route	1	0.405	0.405	0.162	82.434	<0.001
Residuals	281	1.381	0.005	0.551		
Total	287	2.506				

800

801

Table 2. Multiple Matrix Regression with Randomization models of morphological variation of Andean and Atlantic forest birds. Only significant models are reported ($p < 0.05$). Analyses are based on pairwise differences matrices of each metric (except resistance metrics). N: sample size. R^2 : coefficient of determination. I: intercept. Biog_reg: Biogeographic Region (i.e., Andes or Atlantic Forest). PC1_{Temp}: Principal Component (PC) 1 of Temperature Distance. PC2_{Temp}: PC 2 of Temperature Distance. PC1_{Prec}: PC 1 of Precipitation. PC2_{Prec}: PC 2 of Precipitation. R_{PAST}: Past Resistance. R_{CUR}: Current Resistance. Sex: Sex. Gen: Genetic Lineage. Obs: observer.

Species	N	Dependant metric (morphological variation)	Model result		Regression model
			R^2	p-value	
<i>Syndactyla rufosuperciliata</i>	234	PC1_Bill ¹	0.184	0.001	PC1_Bill = I* + 0.45Biog_reg + 0.09PC1 _{Temp} - 0.11R _{CUR} + 0.02Sex
		Wing ¹	0.04	0.001	Wing = I* + 0.19Biog_reg + 0.05PC2 _{Temp} - 0.16R _{CUR} + 0.05Sex
<i>Phylloscartes ventralis</i>	42	PC2_Bill ²	0.151	0.004	PC2_Bill = I* + 0.34PC1 _{Prec}
		Wing ²	0.118	0.001	Wing = I* + 0.32Sex
<i>Poecilatriccus plumbeiceps</i>	67	PC1_Bill ²	0.14	0.001	PC1_Bill = I* - 0.11Biog_reg + 0.19PC2 _{Temp} + 0.07PC2 _{Prec} + 0.2R _{CUR}
		Tarsus ²	0.209	0.001	Tarsus = I* + 0.16Biog_reg + 0.48PC1 _{Temp} - 0.09PC2 _{Temp}
	187	PC1_Bill ²	0.027	0.048	PC1_Bill = 0.13Biog_reg

<i>Arremon dorbignii</i> (Andean)/		Wing ²	0.036	0.013	Wing = 0.04Biog_reg + 0.12R _{CUR} + 0.15Sex
<i>A. flavirostris</i> (Atlantic)					
		PC1_Bill ²	0.066	0.043	PC1_Bill = 0.23Sex
<i>Cacicus chrysopterus</i>	47	Tarsus ²	0.047	0.049	Tarsus = 0.16Biog_reg + 0.08Sex – 0.25Gen
		Wing ²	0.137	0.001	Wing = 0.32Sex
		PC1_Bill ^{1,3}	0.092	0.001	PC1_Bill = I* + 0.09PC1 _{Temp} + 0.05Sex + 0.22Obs
<i>Trichothraupis melanops</i>	205	PC2_Bill ^{1,3}	0.141	0.001	PC2_Bill = I* + 0.19Biog_reg + 0.27Obs
		Tarsus ^{1,3}	0.064	0.003	Tarsus = I* + 0.12Biog_reg – 0.07PC2 _{Prec} + 0.15R _{PAST} + 0.08Obs
		Wing ^{1,3}	0.075	0.001	Wing = I* + 0.25Sex + 0.08Obs
<i>Pipraeidea melanonota</i>	59	Wing ¹	0.142	0.002	Wing = 0.37Sex

¹, data from this study. ², data from Trujillo et al 2020. ³, Data from Cavarzere et al 2024.

* All intercept were very low (<10⁻¹⁴).

803

804

805 **Figure legends**

806

807 **Figure 1.** Study area and working hypotheses on the connection and biological diversification between
808 macrorefugia. The connection hypotheses are: I) Hypothesis of connection between Andean and Atlantic
809 forests through the Cerrado, and II) hypothesis of connection between forests through the Chaco (i.e., through
810 the course of the Bermejo and Pilcomayo Rivers). The hypotheses of diversification between macrorefugia are:
811 I) Andean and Atlantic forests as a refugia system; and II) high historical gene flow between these forests
812 promoting phenotypic homogeneity. The inset map indicates the study region. Predictions of the hypotheses
813 of diversification are based on phenotypic divergence between regions (see also Trujillo-Arias et al. 2020).

814

815 **Figure 2.** Temporal variation in habitat suitability range and connectivity of bird lineages ($n = 24$) with disjunct
816 populations or sublineages in the Andean and Atlantic domains. A, box and whiskers of habitat suitability
817 ranges derived from binary ecological niche models ($n=24$). Average range is denoted by yellow dots, while
818 mean min-max normalized range is shown as black dots. A smoothed dotted line (Wickham 2016) connected
819 mean normalized ranges. B, conductance between Andean and Atlantic forests bird lineages ($n=24$) over time
820 and through two routes. Average conductance is depicted as colored circles, with min-max normalized average
821 values connected by a LOESS smoothed dotted line. Study periods are: Present (1979 — 2013), Mid-Holocene
822 (MH, 8.32 — 4.20 kilo years ago —ka—), Early Holocene (EH, 11.70 — 4.32 ka), Heinrich Stadial 1 (HS1, 17.00
823 — 14.70 ka), Last Glacial Maximum (LGM, ca. 21 ka) and Last Interglacial (LIG, ca. 130 ka).

824

825 **Figure 3.** Accumulated bird lineages ($n = 24$) connectivity between Andean and Atlantic forests during different
826 time periods, as obtained in Circuitscape. For each period, graphs have been generated by adding individual
827 lineages connectivity maps. Current flow values have been standardized before plotting. Average conductance
828 and average min-max normalized (norm.) conductance between forests is indicated for each period and route
829 (N, north route; S, south route). Period ages are in kilo-years ago (ka).

830

831 **Figure 4.** Ecological niche divergence between populations and sister lineages of birds ($n = 24$) from the
832 Andean and Atlantic forests. The graph (left) presents the distribution of the Schoener's D in the sample of
833 study models, and the table (right) presents the percentage of result types of the Background Tests.

834 Interpretation of Schoener's D is as: D = 0 indicates no niche overlapping, while D = 1 indicates full niche
835 overlapping. Results of Background Tests are classified according to three type categories: LTC = statistic D
836 "lower than expected by chance" ($p < 0.01$); NS = Not significant ($p > 0.01$); HTC = statistic D "higher than
837 expected by chance" ($p < 0.01$). We indicate the orientation of the comparison (i.e., Andes to Atlantic Forest
838 and vice versa).

839 **Figures**

840 **Figure 1:**

841

842

843 **Figure 2:**

844

845

846

847

848 **Figure 3:**

849

850

851

852

853 **Figure 4:**

Result type	Background Tests	
	Andes to Atlantic	Atlantic to Andes
LTC	0 %	0%
NS	79.2%	50%
HTC	20.8%	50%

854

855

856